

Prepositional adverbials in French in Quebec (Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean). Appendix: Statistical Measures (Project Materials) [Tables]

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1. INTRODUCTION

These project materials are to be understood as an appendix to a book chapter by Inka Wissner, Inka and Melissa Gagnon, “Adverbials with preposition and adjective in Eastern Quebec (Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean)”, forthcoming in De Gruyter. They provide detailed tables illustrating the exact measures realized on Quebec French data retrieved by Melissa Gagnon during sociolinguistic field work in Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean from 2021 to 2022 with thirty-four informants within the *Third Way* project on prepositional adverbials from Latin to Romance, a project led by Martin Hummel at the University of Graz (Austria)**. Measures are realized according to a method prepared from 2020 to 2021 by Wissner and Roy using Roy’s calculator (Roy 2021-2022), completed by standard probability testing, mentioned in footnotes, using the Fisher-Freeman-Halton test (Lowry 1998-2023). It has been applied to all Romance languages under study in the Third Way project. The linguistic method for data collection has been developed from 2018 to 2020 (Wissner 2023), linguistic data processing from 2020 to 2022 (Wissner forthcoming).

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**2. The Third Way: Project material on Quebec French
Tables with statistical measures**

**2.1 The adverbials' recognition by the informants
in their surrounding and their dialect (A.1-A.2)**

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	La Value on a scale of 0 to 10	Lb Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	IIa Value (scale 0-10)	IIb Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 1: En bref</i>	0.3	0	29 (85%)	5 (15%)	1.6+1.5 / -1.1 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -1.0]		0.3	0	30 (88%)	4 (12%)	1.3+1.4 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -0.9]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	14 (82%)	3 (18%)	2.0+2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]	$p = 0.67$ Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5+2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5+2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]		0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5+2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	17 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9+1.9 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -0.7]	$p = 0.16$ Not sign.	0.6	0	18 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4+1.5 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	$p = 0.06$ Not sign. ¹
Elder speakers	0.6	0	12 (75%)	4 (25%)	2.7+2.5 / -2.0 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -1.7]		0.6	0	12 (75%)	4 (25%)	2.7+2.5 / -2.0 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	7	1	1.8+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.86$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.32$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	10	0	0.6+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.15$	1.0	0	10	0	0.6+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.22$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	7	1	1.8+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.86$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.98$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	5	3	3.9+3.6 / -3.2 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.7]	$p = 0.26$	1.3	0	5	3	3.9+3.6 / -3.2 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.7]	$p = 0.21$
	Lb significance (P =), comparison between age-groups						IIb significance (P =), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				$p = 0.39$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.27$				$p = 0.90$	$p = 0.46$	$p = 0.08$
Speakers aged 30 to 45					$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.07$					$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.07$
Speakers aged 46 to 65						$p = 0.27$						$p = 0.27$
Speakers aged 66 or more												
<i>Item 2: Par "cic"</i>	0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]		0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]	

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

¹ Weak dependency with Fisher ($p = 0.04$).

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 3: Pour de bon	0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]		0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	p = 0.96 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	p = 0.96 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.93	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.93
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
	I.b significance (P =), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P =), comparison age-groups					
Speakers aged 18 to 29			p = 0.93	p = 1.0	p = 1.0				p = 0.93	p = 1.0	p = 1.0	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				p = 0.93	p = 0.93					p = 0.93	p = 0.93	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					p = 1.0						p = 1.0	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 4: (*)De fixe	0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]		0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]	

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 5: Pour certain	0.3	0	27 (79%)	7 (21%)	2.2 +1.6 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -1.2]		0.3	2 (6%)	27 (79%)	5 (15%)	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -1.0]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	14 (82%)	3 (18%)	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]	p = 0.7 Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	14 (82%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	p = 0.67 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	13 (76%)	4 (24%)	2.5 +2.4 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -1.7]		0.6	1 (6%)	13 (76%)	3 (18%)	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	15 (83%)	3 (17%)	1.9 +2.2 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.4]	p = 0.58 Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	15 (83%)	2 (11%)	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	p = 0.57 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	12 (75%)	4 (25%)	2.7 +2.5 / -2.0 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -1.7]		0.6	1 (6%)	12 (75%)	3 (19%)	2.1 +2.4 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	6	2	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	p = 0.82	1.3	1	6	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	p = 0.89
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	9	1	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -1.2]	p = 0.41	1.0	0	9	1	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -1.2]	p = 0.68
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	5	3	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.7]	p = 0.41	1.3	1	5	2	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	p = 0.57
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	p = 0.6	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	p = 0.89
	I.b significance (P =), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P =), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				p = 0.42	p = 0.6	p = 0.55				p = 0.84	p = 0.55	p = 1.0
Speakers aged 30 to 45					p = 0.19	p = 0.84					p = 0.42	p = 0.84
Speakers aged 46 to 65						p = 0.27						p = 0.55
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 6: En continu	0.3	0	7 (21%)	27 (79%)	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -1.6]		0.3	2 (6%)	9 (26%)	23 (68%)	6.7 +1.6 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	3 (18%)	14 (82%)	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.4]	p = 0.72 Not sign.	0.6	2 (12%)	4 (24%)	11 (64%)	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]	p = 0.74 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	4 (24%)	13 (76%)	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.4]		0.6	0 (0%)	5 (29%)	12 (71%)	6.9 +2.1 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	2	16	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	p = 0.22	0.6	1	2	15	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	p = 0.06

			(11%)	(89%)	[83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.2]	Not sign.		(6%)	(11%)	(83%)	[83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	5	11	6.7 +2.2 / -2.9		0.6	1	7	8	5.0 +2.5 / -2.7	
			(31%)	(69%)	[83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.5]			(6%)	(44%)	(50%)	[83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.3]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	$p = 0.63$	1.3	1	1	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	$p = 0.67$
					[83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]						[83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	$p = 0.46$	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	$p = 0.15$
					[83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]						[83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p = 0.18$	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	$p = 0.67$
					[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	5	3	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	$p = 0.05$	1.3	1	5	2	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	$p = 0.04$
					[83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.7]						[83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.54$	$p = 0.05$			$p = 0.47$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.05$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.64$	$p = 0.03$				$p = 0.47$	$p = 0.01$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 0.01$					$p = 0.05$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
Categories exclusive Answers in absolute numbers and %	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 7: <i>À drette</i>	0.3	0	15 (44%)	19 (56%)	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.7]		0.3	0	15 (44%)	19 (56%)	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	7 (41%)	10 (59%)	5.8 +2.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -2.4]	$p = 0.75$	0.6	0	7 (41%)	10 (59%)	5.8 +2.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -2.4]	$p = 0.75$
Male speakers	0.6	0	8 (47%)	9 (53%)	5.3 +2.4 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	8 (47%)	9 (53%)	5.3 +2.4 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	11 (61%)	7 (39%)	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.0]	$p = 0.05$	0.6	0	11 (61%)	7 (39%)	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.0]	$p = 0.05$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	4 (25%)	12 (75%)	7.3 +2.0 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.5]	Not sign.	0.6	0	4 (25%)	12 (75%)	7.3 +2.0 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.5]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	$p = 0.82$	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	$p = 0.82$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	8	2	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	$p = 0.03$	1.0	0	8	2	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.39$	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.39$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.4$	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.4$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.07$	$p = 0.62$	$p = 0.62$				$p = 0.07$	$p = 0.62$	$p = 0.62$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.02$					$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.02$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 8.1: En especial</i>	0.3	0	32 (94%)	2 (6%)	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]		0.3	0	32 (94%)	2 (6%)	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	$p = 0.27$	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	$p = 0.27$
Male speakers	0.6	0	17 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	17 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	17 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +1.9 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -0.7]	$p = 0.92$	0.6	0	17 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +1.9 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -0.7]	$p = 0.92$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.66$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.66$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	10	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.49$	1.0	0	10	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.49$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.67$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.67$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.46$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.46$	$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.90$	$p = 0.39$					$p = 0.90$	$p = 0.39$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 0.46$						$p = 0.46$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 8.2: En spécial</i>	0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.2]		0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.4 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	p = 0.96 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.4 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	p = 0.96 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.93	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.93
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				p = 0.93	p = 1.0	p = 1.0				p = 0.93	p = 1.0	p = 1.0
Speakers aged 30 to 45					p = 0.93	p = 0.93					p = 0.93	p = 0.93
Speakers aged 46 to 65						p = 1.0						p = 1.0
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 9: À l'extrême</i>	0.3	0	4 (12%)	30 (88%)	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -1.5]		0.3	0	4 (12%)	30 (88%)	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -1.5]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	3 (18%)	14 (82%)	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.4]	p = 0.42 Not sign.	0.6	0	3 (18%)	14 (82%)	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.4]	p = 0.42 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]		0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	2	16	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	p = 0.91	0.6	0	2	16	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	p = 0.91

			(11%)	(89%)	[83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.2]	Not sign.			(11%)	(89%)	[83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.2]	Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	2	14	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8		0.6	0	2	14	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	
			(12%)	(88%)	[83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]				(12%)	(88%)	[83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p = 0.47$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p = 0.47$
					[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	2	8	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	$p = 0.65$	1.0	0	2	8	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	$p = 0.65$
					[83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]						[83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p = 0.47$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p = 0.47$
					[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	$p = 0.48$	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	$p = 0.48$
					[83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.35$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.26$				$p = 0.35$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.26$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.35$	$p = 0.8$					$p = 0.35$	$p = 0.8$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 0.26$						$p = 0.26$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
Categories exclusive Answers in absolute numbers and %	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 10: <i>En gros</i>	0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]		0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	$p = 0.35$	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	$p = 0.35$
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.32$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.32$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	2 (12%)	14 (88%)	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]	Not sign.	0.6	0	2 (12%)	14 (88%)	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.69$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.69$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.59$	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.59$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.69$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.69$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.33$	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.33$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.26$				$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.26$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.21$					$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.21$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.26$						$p = 0.26$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 11: À l'improviste</i>	0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]		0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 1.0$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 1.0$
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.96$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.96$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.93$	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.93$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$					$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (P)* (p)	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (P)* (p)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 12: Au large	0.3	0	4 (12%)	30 (88%)	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -1.5]		0.3	0	6 (18%)	28 (82%)	8.1 +1.2 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -1.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	p = 0.42	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	p = 0.13
Male speakers	0.6	0	3 (18%)	14 (82%)	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.4]	Not sign.	0.6	0	5 (29%)	12 (71%)	6.9 +2.1 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -2.4]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	3 (17%)	15 (83%)	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.3]	p = 0.48	0.6	0	3 (17%)	15 (83%)	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.3]	p = 0.88
Elder speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	3 (19%)	13 (81%)	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -2.5]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.49	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.28
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	3	7	6.8 +2.6 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.2]	p = 0.32	1.0	0	3	7	6.8 +2.6 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.2]	p = 0.51
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.49	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.28
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	p = 0.91	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	p = 0.32
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		p = 0.17	p = 1.0	p = 0.54				p = 0.17	p = 1.0	p = 0.11		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			p = 0.17	p = 0.46					p = 0.17	p = 0.74		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				p = 0.54						p = 0.11		
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 13: De léger	0.3	0	32 (94%)	2 (6%)	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]		0.3	0	32 (94%)	2 (6%)	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	p = 1.0	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	p = 1.0
Male speakers	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	Not sign.	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	18	0	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	p = 0.24	0.6	0	18	0	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	p = 0.24

			(100%)	(0%)	[83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	Not sign.			(100%)	(0%)	[83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	14 (87%)	2 (13%)	1.5+2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]		0.6	0	14 (87%)	2 (13%)	1.5+2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	10	0	0.6+2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.48$	1.0	0	10	0	0.6+2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.48$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	6	2	2.9+3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.29$	1.3	0	6	2	2.9+3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.29$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$
I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups						
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.2$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.2$	$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.16$	$p = 0.9$					$p = 0.16$	$p = 0.9$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 0.2$						$p = 0.2$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 14: À plein	0.3	0	15 (44%)	19 (56%)	5.6+1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.7]		0.3	0	15 (44%)	19 (56%)	5.6+1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	6 (35%)	11 (65%)	6.4+2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]	$p = 0.34$	0.6	0	6 (35%)	11 (65%)	6.4+2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]	$p = 0.34$
Male speakers	0.6	0	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7+2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	Not sign.	0.6	0	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7+2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	13 (72%)	5 (28%)	2.9+2.4 / -2.0 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -1.8]	$p=0.001$ Sign., high depend.	0.6	0	13 (72%)	5 (28%)	2.9+2.4 / -2.0 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -1.8]	$p=0.001$ Sign., high depend.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	2 (13%)	14 (87%)	8.5+1.4 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]		0.6	0	2 (13%)	14 (87%)	8.5+1.4 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	6	2	2.9+3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.1$	1.3	0	6	2	2.9+3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.1$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	7	3	3.2+3.3 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.8 / -2.3]	$p = 0.14$	1.0	0	7	3	3.2+3.3 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.8 / -2.3]	$p = 0.14$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	1	7	8.2+1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.11$	1.3	0	1	7	8.2+1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.11$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	1	7	8.2+1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.11$	1.3	0	1	7	8.2+1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.11$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.85$	$p = 0.01$	$p = 0.01$				$p = 0.85$	$p = 0.01$	$p = 0.01$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.02$					$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.02$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
<i>Item 15: De *plene</i>	0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]		0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]	

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 16: De sec</i>	0.3	1 (3%)	31 (91%)	2 (6%)	0.8+1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]		0.3	1 (3%)	31 (91%)	2 (6%)	0.8+1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	0 (0%)	0.4+1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	$p = 0.27$	0.6	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	0 (0%)	0.4+1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	$p = 0.27$
Male speakers	0.6	0 (0%)	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5+2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	Not sign.	0.6	0 (0%)	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5+2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	15 (83%)	2 (11%)	1.4+2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	$p = 0.3$	0.6	1 (6%)	15 (83%)	2 (11%)	1.4+2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	$p = 0.3$
Elder speakers	0.6	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4+1.7 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4+1.7 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.68$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.68$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	1	7	2	2.4+3.2 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	$p = 0.37$	1.0	1	7	2	2.4+3.2 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	$p = 0.37$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7	$p = 0.68$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7	$p = 0.68$

	1.3	0	8	0	[83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6] 0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.68$	1.3	0	8	0	[83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6] 0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.68$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.28$		$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.28$		$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.28$						$p = 0.28$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 17: D'ordinaire</i>	0.3	0	3 (9%)	31 (91%)	9.0 +0.9 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -1.4]		0.3	0	3 (9%)	31 (91%)	9.0 +0.9 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -1.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	$p = 0.68$	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	$p = 0.68$
Male speakers	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	3 (17%)	15 (83%)	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.3]	$p = 0.22$	0.6	0	3 (17%)	15 (83%)	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.3]	$p = 0.22$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.8$	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.8$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	2	8	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]	$p = 0.53$	1.0	0	2	8	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]	$p = 0.53$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.6$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.6$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.6$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.6$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.76$		$p = 0.54$				$p = 0.76$		$p = 0.54$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.35$						$p = 0.35$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
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<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 18: Pour le sûr	0.3	1 (3%)	31 (91%)	2 (6%)	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]		0.3	1 (3%)	31 (91%)	2 (6%)	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	15 (88%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	15 (88%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0 (0%)	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]		0.6	0 (0%)	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	
Younger speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	17 (94%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	$p = 0.24$	0.6	1 (6%)	17 (94%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	$p = 0.24$
Elder speakers	0.6	0 (0%)	14 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]	Not sign.	0.6	0 (0%)	14 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.62$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	1	9	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.49$	1.0	1	9	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.49$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.67$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.67$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.67$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.67$
		I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups				
		18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.46$	$p = 0.46$				$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.46$	$p = 0.46$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.39$					$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.39$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 19: Au sérieux	0.3	0	1 (3%)	33 (97%)	9.5 +0.5 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -1.3]		0.3	0	1 (3%)	33 (97%)	9.5 +0.5 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -1.3]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.61$ Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.61$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]		0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.57$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.57$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.

Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.85$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.85$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.75$	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.75$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.85$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.85$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.58$	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.58$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.54$				$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.54$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.47$					$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.47$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.54$						$p = 0.54$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 20: Pour vrai	0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]		0.3	0	2 (6%)	30 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.35$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.35$
Male speakers	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	2 (13%)	13 (87%)	8.4 +1.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.5]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	17 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -2.1]	$p = 0.93$	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	$p = 1.0$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.72$	1.3	0	0	6	9.1 +0.9 / -4.8 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -4.1]	$p = 0.83$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	$p = 0.83$	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	$p = 0.86$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	$p = 0.68$	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	$p = 0.71$

	1.3	0	0	8	[83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6] 9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.72$	1.3	0	0	8	[83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6] 9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.70$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.64$	$p = 0.54$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.75$	$p = 0.63$	$p = 0.9$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.64$				$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.64$			
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.54$					$p = 0.54$			
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 21: En brave</i>	0.3	2 (6%)	6 (18%)	26 (76%)	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -1.6]		0.3	2 (6%)	6 (18%)	26 (76%)	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -1.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	2 (12%)	4 (24%)	11 (64%)	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]	$p = 0.16$	0.6	2 (12%)	4 (24%)	11 (64%)	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]	$p = 0.16$
Male speakers	0.6	0 (0%)	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0 (0%)	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	4 (22%)	13 (72%)	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.4]	$p = 0.6$	0.6	1 (6%)	4 (22%)	13 (72%)	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.4]	$p = 0.6$
Elder speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	2 (13%)	13 (81%)	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -2.5]	Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	2 (13%)	13 (81%)	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -2.5]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	1	2	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	$p = 0.5$	1.3	1	2	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	$p = 0.5$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	2	8	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]	$p = 0.81$	1.0	0	2	8	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]	$p = 0.81$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	1	0	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.55$	1.3	1	0	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.55$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.94$	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.94$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.45$	$p = 0.3$	$p = 0.62$				$p = 0.45$	$p = 0.3$	$p = 0.62$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.76$	$p = 0.8$				$p = 0.76$	$p = 0.8$			
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.59$					$p = 0.59$			
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
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<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 22: De court	0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]		0.4	0	2 (7%)	26 (93%)	9.1 +0.8 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -1.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.35 Not sign.	0.7	0	0 (0%)	15 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.29 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]		0.8	0	2 (15%)	11 (85%)	8.1 +1.7 / -3.2 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.8]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	17 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -2.1]	<i>p</i> = 0.93 Not sign.	0.8	0	1 (8%)	12 (92%)	8.8 +1.2 / -3.1 [83 % CI: +1.0 / -2.7]	<i>p</i> = 0.92 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]		0.7	0	1 (7%)	14 (93%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.72	2.0	0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.85
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.83	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.78
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.72	1.4	0	0	7	9.2 +0.8 / -4.4 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -3.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.69
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.68	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.78
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				<i>p</i> = 0.64	<i>p</i> = 1.0	<i>p</i> = 0.54				<i>p</i> = 0.70	<i>p</i> = 0.88	<i>p</i> = 0.70
Speakers aged 30 to 45					<i>p</i> = 0.64	<i>p</i> = 0.86					<i>p</i> = 0.58	<i>p</i> = 1.0
Speakers aged 46 to 65						<i>p</i> = 0.54						<i>p</i> = 0.58
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 23: À mal	0.3	0	29 (85%)	5 (15%)	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -1.0]		0.3	0	29 (85%)	5 (15%)	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -1.0]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	<i>p</i> = 0.67 Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	<i>p</i> = 0.67 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	14 (82%)	3 (18%)	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]		0.6	0	14 (82%)	3 (18%)	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	15 (83%)	3 (17%)	1.9 +2.2 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.78 Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (83%)	3 (17%)	1.9 +2.2 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.78 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	14 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]		0.6	0	14 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]	

Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	7	1	1.8+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.91$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8+3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.91$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	8	2	2.4+3.2 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	$p = 0.76$	1.0	0	8	2	2.4+3.2 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	$p = 0.76$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	6	2	2.9+3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.55$	1.3	0	6	2	2.9+3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.55$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.26$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.26$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.74$	$p = 0.55$	$p = 0.46$				$p = 0.74$	$p = 0.55$	$p = 0.46$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.78$	$p = 0.28$					$p = 0.78$	$p = 0.28$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.2$						$p = 0.2$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
<i>Item 24: De *diaire</i>	0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]		0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]	
<i>Item 25: (*)De seguide</i>	0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]		0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2+0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 26: À blanc</i>	0.3	0	30 (88%)	4 (12%)	1.3+1.4 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -0.9]		0.3	0	30 (88%)	4 (12%)	1.3+1.4 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -0.9]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9+2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	$p = 0.36$ Not sign.	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9+2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	$p = 0.36$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	14 (82%)	3 (18%)	2.0+2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]		0.6	0	14 (82%)	3 (18%)	2.0+2.3 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.4]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	16 (89%)	2 (11%)	1.4+2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	$p = 0.89$ Not sign.	0.6	0	16 (89%)	2 (11%)	1.4+2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	$p = 0.89$ Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	14 (87%)	2 (13%)	1.5+2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]		0.6	0	14 (87%)	2 (13%)	1.5+2.3 / -1.4 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7	$p = 0.37$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7+3.0 / -0.7	$p = 0.37$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	8	2	[83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6] 2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	$p = 0.62$	1.0	0	8	2	[83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6] 2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	$p = 0.62$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	8	0	[83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8] 0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	$p = 0.37$	1.3	0	8	0	[83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8] 0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	$p = 0.37$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	6	2	[83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6] 2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	$p = 0.44$	1.3	0	6	2	[83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6] 2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	$p = 0.44$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.28$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.20$				$p = 0.28$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.20$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.28$	$p = 0.78$				$p = 0.28$	$p = 0.78$			
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.20$					$p = 0.20$			
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 27: En clair</i>	0.3	3 (9%)	18 (53%)	13 (38%)	3.9 +1.8 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.5]		0.3	3 (9%)	18 (53%)	13 (38%)	3.9 +1.8 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.5]	
Female speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	9 (53%)	7 (41%)	4.2 +2.5 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.1]	$p = 0.74$	0.6	1 (6%)	9 (53%)	7 (41%)	4.2 +2.5 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.1]	$p = 0.74$
Male speakers	0.6	2 (12%)	9 (53%)	6 (35%)	3.6 +2.5 / -2.3 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.0]	Not sign.	0.6	2 (12%)	9 (53%)	6 (35%)	3.6 +2.5 / -2.3 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.0]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	2 (12%)	8 (44%)	8 (44%)	4.5 +2.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.1]	$p = 0.46$	0.6	2 (12%)	8 (44%)	8 (44%)	4.5 +2.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.1]	$p = 0.46$
Elder speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	10 (63%)	5 (31%)	3.3 +2.6 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -1.9]	Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	10 (63%)	5 (31%)	3.3 +2.6 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -1.9]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	2	4	2	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.52$	1.3	2	4	2	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.52$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	4	6	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.24$	1.0	0	4	6	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.24$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	$p = 0.53$	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	$p = 0.53$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	1	6	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.15$	1.3	1	6	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.15$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.15$	$p = 0.31$	$p = 0.55$				$p = 0.15$	$p = 0.31$	$p = 0.55$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.68$	$p = 0.04$				$p = 0.68$	$p = 0.04$			
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.11$					$p = 0.11$			
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 28: À couvert	0.3	0	16 (47%)	18 (53%)	5.3 +1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.6]		0.3	0	16 (50%)	16 (50%)	5.0 +1.8 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	7 (41%)	10 (59%)	5.8 +2.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -2.4]	p = 0.53	0.7	0	7 (47%)	8 (53%)	5.3 +2.6 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.5]	p = 0.74
Male speakers	0.6	0	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	Not sign.	0.6	0	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.2]	p = 0.74	0.6	0	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.2]	p = 1.0
Elder speakers	0.6	0	7 (44%)	9 (56%)	5.6 +2.4 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.4]	Not sign.	0.7	0	7 (50%)	7 (50%)	5.0 +2.7 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +2.3 / -2.5]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.88	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.97
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	5	5	5.0 +3.1 / -3.3 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -2.9]	p = 0.88	1.0	0	5	5	5.0 +3.1 / -3.3 [83 % CI: +2.7 / -2.9]	p = 0.97
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	p = 0.65	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	p = 0.53
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.88	1.7	0	4	2	3.6 +4.1 / -3.3 [83 % CI: +3.5 / -2.8]	p = 0.48
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				p = 1.0	p = 0.63	p = 1.0				p = 1.0	p = 0.63	p = 0.54
Speakers aged 30 to 45					p = 0.62	p = 1.0					p = 0.62	p = 0.53
Speakers aged 46 to 65						p = 0.63						p = 0.28
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 29: En dernier	0.3	1 (3%)	17 (50%)	16 (47%)	4.7 +1.8 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.6]		0.3	1 (3%)	19 (56%)	14 (41%)	4.2 +1.8 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -1.5]	
Female speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	9 (53%)	7 (41%)	4.2 +2.5 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.1]	p = 0.52	0.6	1 (6%)	10 (59%)	6 (35%)	3.6 +2.5 / -2.3 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.0]	p = 0.52
Male speakers	0.6	0 (0%)	8 (47%)	9 (53%)	5.3 +2.4 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0 (0%)	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	1	10	7	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3	p = 0.35	0.6	1	10	7	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3	p = 0.79

		(6%)	(55%)	(39%)	[83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.0]	Not sign.		(6%)	(55%)	(39%)	[83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.0]	Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	7	9	5.6 +2.4 / -2.8		0.6	0	9	7	4.4 +2.6 / -2.6	
		(0%)	(44%)	(56%)	[83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.4]			(0%)	(56%)	(44%)	[83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	$p = 0.5$	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	$p = 0.33$
					[83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]						[83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	1	7	2	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	$p = 0.1$	1.0	1	7	2	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	$p = 0.18$
					[83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]						[83 % CI: +2.7 / -1.8]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	$p = 0.94$	1.3	0	6	2	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	$p = 0.36$
					[83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]						[83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.2]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	$p = 0.5$	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	$p = 0.33$
					[83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]						[83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.07$	$p = 0.63$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.07$	$p = 0.14$	$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.19$	$p = 0.07$					$p = 0.78$	$p = 0.07$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.63$						$p = 0.14$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 30: Par exprès</i>	0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]		0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	p = 0.96 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	p = 0.96 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.93	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.93
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.98
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
Speakers aged 18 to 29			p = 0.93	p = 1.0	p = 1.0				p = 0.93	p = 1.0	p = 1.0	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				p = 0.93	p = 0.93					p = 0.93	p = 0.93	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					p = 1.0						p = 1.0	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 31: En grand</i>	0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]		0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	p = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	p = 0.96	0.6	0	0	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	p = 0.96

			(0%)	(100%)	[83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	Not sign.			(0%)	(100%)	[83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5		0.6	0	0	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	
			(0%)	(100%)	[83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]				(0%)	(100%)	[83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p=0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p=0.98$
					[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	$p=0.93$	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	$p=0.93$
					[83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]						[83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p=0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p=0.98$
					[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p=0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	$p=0.98$
					[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]						[83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$					$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 32: Allège</i>	0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]		0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.35$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.35$
Male speakers	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	2 (12%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	2 (11%)	16 (89%)	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.39$	0.6	0	2 (11%)	16 (89%)	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.2]	$p = 0.39$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.68$	1.3	0	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	$p = 0.68$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	$p = 0.83$	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	$p = 0.83$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.72$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.72$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.72$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.72$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.54$	$p = 0.54$				$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.54$	$p = 0.54$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.64$	$p = 0.64$					$p = 0.64$	$p = 0.64$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 33: Au long</i>	0.3	0	31 (91%)	3 (9%)	1.0 +1.3 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -0.7]		0.3	0	31 (91%)	3 (9%)	1.0 +1.3 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -0.7]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	$p = 0.62$	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	$p = 0.62$
Male speakers	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (88%)	2 (12%)	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -1.1]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	16 (89%)	2 (11%)	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	$p = 0.7$	0.6	0	16 (89%)	2 (11%)	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -1.1]	$p = 0.7$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.79$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.79$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	9	1	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -1.2]	$p = 0.98$	1.0	0	9	1	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -1.2]	$p = 0.98$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.79$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.79$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.48$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.48$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29		30-45	46-65	> 65		18 to 29		30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29			$p = 0.84$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.46$				$p = 0.84$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.46$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45				$p = 0.84$	$p = 0.57$					$p = 0.84$	$p = 0.57$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65					$p = 0.46$						$p = 0.46$	
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 34: En neuf	0.3	0	8 (24%)	26 (76%)	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -1.6]		0.3	0	8 (24%)	26 (76%)	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -1.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	4 (24%)	13 (76%)	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.4]	p = 1.0 Not sign.	0.6	0	4 (24%)	13 (76%)	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.4]	p = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	4 (24%)	13 (76%)	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.4]		0.6	0	4 (24%)	13 (76%)	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	5 (28%)	13 (72%)	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.4]	p = 0.6 Not sign.	0.6	0	5 (28%)	13 (72%)	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.4]	p = 0.6 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	3 (19%)	13 (81%)	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -2.5]		0.6	0	3 (19%)	13 (81%)	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -2.5]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.22	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.22
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	p = 0.36	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	p = 0.36
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	p = 0.52	1.3	0	3	5	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9 [83 % CI: +2.6 / -3.4]	p = 0.52
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.14	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	p = 0.14
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				p = 0.09	p = 0.63	p = 0.04				p = 0.09	p = 0.63	p = 0.04
Speakers aged 30 to 45					p = 0.22	p = 0.64					p = 0.22	p = 0.64
Speakers aged 46 to 65						p = 0.11						p = 0.11
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 35: À noir	0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]		0.3	0	34 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -0.2]	

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 36: Au parfait</i>	0.3	0	33 (97%)	1 (3%)	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -0.4]		0.3	0	33 (97%)	1 (3%)	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -0.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	p = 0.52	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	p = 0.52
Male speakers	0.6	0	17 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	Not sign.	0.6	0	17 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	18 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	p = 0.47	0.6	0	18 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	p = 0.47
Elder speakers	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	Not sign.	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	p = 0.81	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	p = 0.81
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	10	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	p = 0.68	1.0	0	10	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	p = 0.68
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	p = 0.52	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	p = 0.52
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	p = 0.81	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	p = 0.81
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				p = 0.90	p = 0.46	p = 1.0				p = 0.90	p = 0.46	p = 1.0
Speakers aged 30 to 45					p = 0.39	p = 0.9					p = 0.39	p = 0.9
Speakers aged 46 to 65						p = 0.46						p = 0.46
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 37: À la rebours</i>	0.3	0	33 (97%)	1 (3%)	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -0.4]		0.3	0	33 (97%)	1 (3%)	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -0.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	17 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	p = 0.52	0.6	0	17 (100%)	0 (0%)	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -0.3]	p = 0.52
Male speakers	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	Not sign.	0.6	0	16 (94%)	1 (6%)	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -0.8]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	18	0	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	p = 0.47	0.6	0	18	0	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	p = 0.47

			(100%)	(0%)	[83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	Not sign.			(100%)	(0%)	[83 % CI: +1.3 / -0.3]	Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]		0.6	0	15 (94%)	1 (6%)	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -0.8]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.81$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.81$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	10	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.68$	1.0	0	10	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	$p = 0.68$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.81$	1.3	0	8	0	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -0.6]	$p = 0.81$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.52$	1.3	0	7	1	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +3.0 / -1.5]	$p = 0.52$
I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups						
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.9$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.46$				$p = 0.9$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.46$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.39$					$p = 0.9$	$p = 0.39$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.46$						$p = 0.46$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 38: De travers	0.3	0	2 (6%)	32 (94%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]		0.3	0	2 (7%)	30 (93%)	9.2 +0.7 / -1.6 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -1.4]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	$p = 1.0$	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	$p = 1.0$
Male speakers	0.6	0	1 (6%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	Not sign.	0.6	0	1 (6%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.32$	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 0.31$
Elder speakers	0.6	0	2 (13%)	14 (87%)	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -2.4]	Not sign.	0.7	0	2 (13%)	13 (87%)	8.4 +1.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.5]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.69$	1.3	0	0	7	9.2 +0.8 / -4.4 [83 % CI: +0.7 / -3.8]	$p = 0.7$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.59$	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.53$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	$p = 0.33$	1.3	0	2	5	6.8 +2.8 / -4.3 [83 % CI: +2.4 / -3.7]	$p = 0.29$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.69$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.64$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.26$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.88$	$p = 0.23$	$p = 0.95$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.21$	$p = 0.93$					$p = 0.17$	$p = 0.93$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 0.26$						$p = 0.21$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 39: Pantoute</i>	0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]		0.3	0	0 (0%)	34 (100%)	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3 [83 % CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	17 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.96$ Not sign.	0.6	0	0 (0%)	18 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -1.9]	$p = 0.96$ Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]		0.6	0	0 (0%)	16 (100%)	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5 [83 % CI: +0.3 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.93$	1.0	0	0	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.93$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.98$
	I.b significance ($P =$), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance ($P =$), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.93$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$					$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				$p = 1.0$						$p = 1.0$		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 40: En premier</i>	0.3	2 (6%)	2 (6%)	30 (88%)	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -1.5]		0.3	2 (6%)	4 (12%)	28 (82%)	8.1 +1.2 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -1.6]	
Female speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	16 (94%)	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.42	0.6	1 (6%)	1 (6%)	15 (88%)	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.1 / -2.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.46
Male speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	2 (12%)	14 (82%)	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.4]	Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	3 (18%)	13 (76%)	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.4]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	2 (11%)	15 (83%)	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.3 / -2.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.48	0.6	1 (6%)	4 (22%)	13 (72%)	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.17
Elder speakers	0.6	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.	0.6	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	15 (94%)	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7 [83 % CI: +0.8 / -2.3]	Not sign.
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	1	1	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.49	1.3	1	1	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.67
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	1	9	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.86	1.0	0	3	7	6.8 +2.6 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.51
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	1	0	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.96	1.3	1	0	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.81
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.45	1.3	0	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +0.6 / -3.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.29
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
	18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29		<i>p</i> = 0.47	<i>p</i> = 0.59	<i>p</i> = 0.26				<i>p</i> = 0.85	<i>p</i> = 0.59	<i>p</i> = 0.26		
Speakers aged 30 to 45			<i>p</i> = 0.86	<i>p</i> = 0.64					<i>p</i> = 0.46	<i>p</i> = 0.17		
Speakers aged 46 to 65				<i>p</i> = 0.54						<i>p</i> = 0.54		
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	Recognition 0. Not sure	0. No	10. Yes	I.a Value on a scale of 0 to 10	I.b Significance (p)*	Threshold for unknown	Recognition locally 0. NS	0. No	10. Yes	II.a Value (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)*
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 41: Au ras</i>	0.3	0	15 (44%)	19 (56%)	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.7]		0.3	0	15 (44%)	19 (56%)	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9 [83 % CI: +1.5 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0.6	0	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	p = 0.34 Not sign.	0.6	0	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -2.2]	p = 0.34 Not sign.
Male speakers	0.6	0	6 (35%)	11 (65%)	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]		0.6	0	6 (35%)	11 (65%)	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8 [83 % CI: +1.9 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0.6	0	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.2]	p = 0.5 Not sign.	0.6	0	9 (50%)	9 (50%)	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6 [83 % CI: +2.1 / -2.2]	p = 0.5 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0.6	0	6 (38%)	10 (62%)	6.2 +2.3 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -2.5]		0.6	0	6 (38%)	10 (62%)	6.2 +2.3 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +2.0 / -2.5]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.3	0	5	3	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.7]	p = 0.38	1.3	0	5	3	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2 [83 % CI: +3.1 / -2.7]	p = 0.38
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.0	0	4	6	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.82	1.0	0	4	6	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.82
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	p = 0.34	1.3	0	2	6	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1 [83 % CI: +2.2 / -3.5]	p = 0.34
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.78	1.3	0	4	4	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6 [83 % CI: +2.9 / -3.1]	p = 0.78
	I.b significance (P=), comparison between age-groups						II.b significance (P=), comparison age-groups					
			18-29	30-45	46-65	> 65			18 to 29	30 to 45	46 to 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29				p = 0.36	p = 0.14	p = 0.62				p = 0.36	p = 0.14	p = 0.62
Speakers aged 30 to 45					p = 0.55	p = 0.68					p = 0.55	p = 0.68
Speakers aged 46 to 65						p = 0.33						p = 0.33
Speakers aged 66 or more												

Table 2.1: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

2. The Third Way: Project material on Quebec French

2.2 The adverbials' frequency as perceived by the informants (B.1)

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 1: En bref	0	4 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	
Female speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...] ²	$p =$
Elder speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	
Item 2: Par *ciec	0	0	0	0	-/-	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 3: Pour de bon	0	0 (0%)	24 (92%)	2 (8%)	9.0 +0.2 / -0.4 [83% CI: +0.1 / -0.4]	
Female speakers	0	0	12	1	9.0 +0.2 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.8]	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0	0	12	1	9.0 +0.2 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.8]	
Younger speakers	0	0	12	2	9.0 +0.2 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.7]	$p = 0.78$ Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	0	12	0	8.9 +0.2 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.8]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	7	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	5	2	9.2 +0.3 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	5	0	8.9 +0.4 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.8]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	7	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.3]	

² When no answer is provided by a group or sub-group (0-0-0) – cases presented in grey – the retained value is reported from A.1 (e.g., for 23 speakers: 0.3 +1.2/-0.3) (cf. Roy's calculator 2020-2022), which essentially corresponds to 23-0-0.

French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 4: *De fixe</i>	0	0	0	0	-/-	
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Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 5: Pour certain</i>	0	7 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4.4 +3.8 / -2.3 [83% CI: +3.3 / -1.9]	
Female speakers	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.84 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	
Younger speakers	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.84 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 6: En continu</i>	0	17 (68%)	8 (32%)	0 (0%)	5.8 +1.2 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.1]	
Female speakers	0	8	5	0	6.5 +1.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.5 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	9	3	0	5.7 +2.0 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.6]	
Younger speakers	0	8	8	0	7.0 +1.1 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.05 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	9	0	0	4.0 +3.6 / -2.0 [83% CI: +3.1 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	5	2	0	6.3 +2.3 / -2.1 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	3	6	0	7.8 +1.1 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	6	0	0	4.6 +3.9 / -2.4 [83% CI: +3.3 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 7: À drette</i>	0	6 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4.6 +3.9 / -2.4 [83% CI: +3.3 / -2.1]	
Female speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.71 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	

Younger speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.71 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -...	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 8.1: En especial</i>	0	2 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Female speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> =
Male speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 8.2: En spécial</i>	0	0 (0%)	14 (41%)	20 (59%)	9.5 +0.1 / -0.4 [83% CI: +0.1 / -0.3]	
Female speakers	0	0	8	9	9.4 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.75 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	0	6	11	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.1 / -0.6]	
Younger speakers	0	0	7	11	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.1 / -0.6]	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	0	7	9	9.5 +0.2 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.7]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	4	4	9.4 +0.2 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	3	7	9.6 +0.2 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	3	5	9.5 +0.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	4	4	9.4 +0.2 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.3]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 9: À l'extrême</i>	0	6 (20%)	22 (73%)	2 (7%)	8.3 +0.5 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0	3	11	0	8.2 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -0.9]	<i>p</i> = 0.74

Male speakers	0	3	11	2	8.4 +0.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.9]	Not sign.
Younger speakers	0	4	10	2	8.2 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -0.9]	<i>p</i> = 0.61 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	2	12	0	8.5 +0.5 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.9]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	5	2	8.8 +0.6 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	3	5	0	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	8	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	2	4	0	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.5]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 10: <i>En gros</i>	0	5 (16%)	21 (65%)	6 (19%)	8.6 +0.4 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0	2	10	3	8.7 +0.5 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.9]	<i>p</i> = 0.72 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	3	11	3	8.5 +0.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.9]	
Younger speakers	0	0	12	6	9.2 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.007 Sign., weak depend.
Elder speakers	0	5	9	0	7.6 +0.9 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	7	1	9.0 +0.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	5	5	9.4 +0.2 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	5	3	0	6.6 +1.9 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.6]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	6	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.5]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 11: <i>À l'improviste</i>	0	6 (18%)	28 (82%)	0 (0%)	8.3 +0.4 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.5]	
Female speakers	0	3	14	0	8.3 +0.5 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	3	14	0	8.3 +0.5 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.8]	
Younger speakers	0	3	15	0	8.4 +0.5 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.85 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	3	13	0	8.3 +0.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.9]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	3	5	0	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	10	0	8.9 +0.2 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.0]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	7	0	8.5 +0.6 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	2	6	0	8.1 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 12: <i>Au large</i>	0	13 (50%)	13 (50%)	0 (0%)	6.9 +0.8 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.8]	
Female speakers	0	7	8	0	7.2 +1.1 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.74 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	6	5	0	6.9 +1.4 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.3]	
Younger speakers	0	6	9	0	7.4 +0.9 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.31 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	7	4	0	6.4 +1.7 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	4	4	0	7.2 +1.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	2	5	0	8.0 +1.1 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	4	2	0	6.6 +2.3 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	2	0	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.7]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 13: <i>De léger</i>	0	2 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Female speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> =
Elder speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 14: <i>À plein</i>	0	14 (74%)	5 (26%)	0 (0%)	5.5 +1.6 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.3]	
Female speakers	0	10	1	0	4.5 +2.9 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.5 / -1.7]	<i>p</i> = 0.07 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	4	4	0	7.2 +1.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	
Younger speakers	0	5	0	0	5.0 +4.1 / -2.6 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.47 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	9	5	0	6.3 +1.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.3]	

Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	6	1	0	5.4 +3.0 / -2.2 [83% CI: +2.6 / -1.9]
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	4	0	7.5 +1.4 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.4]
Item 15: De *plene	0	0	0	0	-/-

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 16: De sec	0	2 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Female speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$
Male speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	$p =$
Elder speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 17: D'ordinaire	0	8 (80%)	2 (20%)	0 (0%)	5.5 +2.4 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.1 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0	6	0	0	4.6 +3.9 / -2.4 [83% CI: +3.3 / -2.1]	$p = 0.15$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0	2	2	0	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.7]	
Younger speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	$p = 0.52$ Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	4	2	0	6.6 +2.3 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	2	2	0	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.7]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 18: Pour le sûr</i>	0	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	
Female speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.62 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.62 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 19: Au sérieux</i>	0	4 (12%)	21 (64%)	8 (24%)	8.8 +0.4 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.5]	
Female speakers	0	0	13	4	9.1 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.11 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	4	8	4	8.3 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.0]	
Younger speakers	0	2	8	8	9.0 +0.4 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.31 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	2	13	0	8.5 +0.5 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.9]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	2	4	2	8.3 +1.0 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	4	6	9.5 +0.2 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	8	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	2	5	0	8.0 +1.1 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.4]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 20: Pour vrai</i>	0	3 (10%)	23 (77%)	4 (13%)	8.7 +0.3 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.5]	
Female speakers	0	2	13	2	8.6 +0.5 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.69 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	1	10	2	8.8 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.9]	
Younger speakers	0	0	11	4	9.2 +0.2 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.7]	<i>p</i> = 0.04 Sign., weak depend.
Elder speakers	0	3	12	0	8.2 +0.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.9]	

Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	6	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	5	4	9.3 +0.2 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	3	4	0	7.5 +1.4 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	8	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 21: <i>En brave</i>	0	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Female speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> =
Male speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> =
Elder speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 22: <i>De court</i>	0	1 (4%)	23 (96%)	0 (0%)	8.8 +0.2 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.5]	
Female speakers	0	1	13	0	8.7 +0.3 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.66 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	0	10	0	8.9 +0.2 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.0]	
Younger speakers	0	0	10	0	8.9 +0.2 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.66 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	1	13	0	8.7 +0.3 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	4	0	9.0 +0.4 / -2.6 [83% CI: +0.4 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	6	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	6	0	8.5 +0.7 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	7	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.3]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 23: <i>À mal</i>	0	2 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Female speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> =
Male speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> =

					[83% CI: +... / -...]	
Elder speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 24: <i>De *diaire</i>	0	0	0	0	-/-	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 25: (*) <i>De seguide</i>	0	0	0	0	-/-	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 26: <i>A blanc</i>	0	2 (50%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.7]	
Female speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.57 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	1	2	0	7.8 +1.7 / -2.4 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.9]	
Younger speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.19 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	0	2	0	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -3.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	2	0	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -3.2]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 27: <i>En clair</i>	0	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Female speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> =
Male speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	<i>p</i> =
Elder speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -...	

Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	[83% CI: +... / -...] ... +... / -...
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 28: À couvert</i>	0	12 (75%)	4 (25%)	0 (0%)	5.5 +1.8 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.4]	
Female speakers	0	6	2	0	6.0 +2.4 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.7]	p = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	6	2	0	6.0 +2.4 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.7]	
Younger speakers	0	6	3	0	6.4 +1.9 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.6]	p = 0.52 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	6	1	0	5.4 +3.0 / -2.2 [83% CI: +2.6 / -1.9]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	3	1	0	6.5 +3.0 / -2.3 [83% CI: +2.4 / -1.9]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	3	2	0	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	5	0	0	5.0 +4.1 / -2.6 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.2]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	1	1	0	7.4 +2.5 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.7]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 29: En dernier</i>	0	9 (60%)	6 (40%)	0 (0%)	6.5 +1.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.2]	
Female speakers	0	6	1	0	5.4 +3.0 / -2.2 [83% CI: +2.6 / -1.9]	p = 0.14 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	3	5	0	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	
Younger speakers	0	6	2	0	6.0 +2.4 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.7]	p = 0.26 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	3	4	0	7.5 +1.4 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	3	2	0	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	3	0	0	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	1	4	0	8.3 +1.0 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.7]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean]	0	0	16	16	9.4 +0.1 / -0.4	

Item 30: Par exprès		(0%)	(50%)	(50%)	[83% CI: +0.1 / -0.3]	
Female speakers	0	0	7	8	9.4 +0.2 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.7]	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	0	9	8	9.4 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	
Younger speakers	0	0	7	11	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.1 / -0.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.39 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	0	9	5	9.2 +0.2 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.8]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	4	4	9.4 +0.2 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	3	7	9.6 +0.2 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	3	5	9.5 +0.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	6	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.5]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 31: En grand	0	0 (0%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	9.1 +0.3 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.3]	
Female speakers	0	0	5	1	9.1 +0.3 / -1.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.84 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	0	1	1	9.4 +0.2 / -5.5 [83% CI: +0.2 / -4.1]	
Younger speakers	0	0	2	0	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -3.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.88 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	0	4	2	9.2 +0.3 / -2.0 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	2	0	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -3.2]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	3	0	9.0 +0.5 / -3.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -2.6]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	1	2	9.4 +0.2 / -4.2 [83% CI: +0.2 / -3.3]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 32: Allège	0	5 (16%)	26 (81%)	1 (3%)	8.4 +0.4 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.5]	
Female speakers	0	4	13	0	8.1 +0.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.17 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	1	13	1	8.8 +0.4 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]	
Younger speakers	0	3	12	1	8.3 +0.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.9]	<i>p</i> = 0.69 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	2	14	0	8.5 +0.4 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.8]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	5	1	8.6 +0.7 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	2	7	0	8.2 +0.8 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	6	0	8.1 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	

Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	8	0	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.2]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 33: Au long</i>	0	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.4]	
Female speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.62 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	
Younger speakers	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI: +2.8 / -2.4]	<i>p</i> = 0.62 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 34: En neuf</i>	0	11 (42%)	14 (54%)	1 (4%)	7.3 +0.8 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.8]	
Female speakers	0	4	8	1	7.9 +0.9 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.1]	<i>p</i> = 0.24 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	7	6	0	6.9 +1.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2]	
Younger speakers	0	7	5	1	6.9 +1.4 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.29 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	4	9	0	7.8 +0.8 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	3	5	1	7.9 +1.1 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.3]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	4	0	8.3 +1.0 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.7]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	5	0	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 35: A noir</i>	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 36: Au parfait</i>	0	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Female speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	<i>p</i> =

Male speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$
Elder speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 37: <i>À la rebours</i>	0	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Female speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$
Male speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	$p =$
Elder speakers	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	1	0	0	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.0]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency <i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 38: <i>De travers</i>	0	3 (15%)	17 (85%)	0 (0%)	8.4 +0.4 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.7]	
Female speakers	0	2	8	0	8.3 +0.7 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	$p = 0.65$ Not sign.
Male speakers	0	1	9	0	8.6 +0.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	
Younger speakers	0	1	8	0	8.6 +0.5 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.2]	$p = 0.65$ Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	2	9	0	8.3 +0.7 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.1]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	3	0	8.1 +1.3 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.8]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	0	5	0	8.9 +0.4 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.8]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	5	0	8.9 +0.4 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.8]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	2	4	0	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.5]	

French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 39: Pantoute</i> ³	0	0	0	0	... +... / -... [83% CI: +... / -...]	
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Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

B.1 Frequency Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II. Value (1-10)	III. Significance of group- dependency (probability)
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 40: En premier</i>	0	6 (21%)	21 (75%)	1 (4%)	8.2 +0.5 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.6]	
Female speakers	0	1	13	1	8.8 +0.4 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]	<i>p</i> = 0.04 Sign. weak depend.
Male speakers	0	5	8	0	7.5 +1.0 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.1]	
Younger speakers	0	1	11	1	8.7 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.9]	<i>p</i> = 0.1 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	5	10	0	7.7 +0.8 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.0]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	5	1	9.1 +0.3 / -1.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.6]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	1	6	0	8.5 +0.7 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	5	0	8.0 +1.1 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	5	0	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 41: Au ras</i>	0	9 (43%)	12 (57%)	0 (0%)	7.3 +0.8 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.9]	
Female speakers	0	4	5	0	7.4 +1.3 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.
Male speakers	0	5	7	0	7.4 +1.1 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.1]	
Younger speakers	0	5	6	0	7.3 +1.2 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.83 Not sign.
Elder speakers	0	4	6	0	7.5 +1.2 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	1	2	0	7.8 +1.7 / -2.4 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.9]	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0	4	4	0	7.2 +1.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	4	0	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	2	2	0	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.7]	

Table 2.2: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

³ Statistical measures based on deduction (high frequency).

2. The Third Way: Project material on Quebec French

2.3 The adverbials' vitality in the informants' speaker group

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom ⁴ (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$) ⁵					
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		$(2 \times A.1 + 1 \times A.2 + 1 \times B.1) - 4$							
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 1: En bref</i>	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1	34	1.3 +1.4 / -1.0	34	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	2.5 +1.4 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.2 / -0.9]	29						
Female speakers	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.0 +1.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.84$ Not sign.					
Male speakers	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29						
Younger speakers	0.9 +1.9 / -0.9	18	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	...	...	0.9 +1.3 / -0.7 [83% CI: +1.1 / -0.6]	29	$p = 0.02$ Significant, weak depend.					
Elder speakers	2.7 +2.5 / -2.0	16	2.7 +2.5 / -2.0	16	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	3.4 +1.7 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.3]	29						
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65		
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	...	...	1.8 +2.4 / -1.3 [83% CI: +2.1 / -1.1]	29	$p = 0.46$		$p = 0.5$	$p = 0.27$	$p = 0.07$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0.6 +3.5 / -1.8	10	0.6 +3.5 / -1.8	10	...	...	0.9 +2.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +2.2 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.13$			$p = 0.08$	$p = 0.02$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.53$				$p = 0.38$	
Speakers aged 66 or more	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	8	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	8	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	4.4 +2.3 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.8]	29	$p = 0.12$					
Jean] <i>Item 2: Par *cior</i>	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	...	...	0.3 +0.6 / -0.2 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.2]	29						

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

⁴ Standard value [29] unless the total is under 29.

⁵ All probability values have been measured using Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Age differences are based on measures using the calculator's 'Vitality' sheet, which reports exact two-tailed uncertainties. The latter has been conceived for the comparison of four sets of data (four age groups). Therefore measures on gender, which require a 2x2 table, have been realized using the calculator's Student's two-sample *t*-test sheet, which is potentially less exact insofar as it averages the two-tailed uncertainties (see Wissner/Roy forthcoming).

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)				
									Weighting / combination	double-weighted	simple-weighted	simple-weighted	(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 3: Pour de bon</i>	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.0 +0.2 / -0.4	26	9.4 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.0 +0.2 / -0.9	13	9.1 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.0 +0.2 / -0.9	13	9.1 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.0 +0.2 / -0.8	14	8.4 +0.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.82 Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	8.9 +0.2 / -0.9	12	8.3 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.6	7	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.97		<i>p</i> = 0.83	<i>p</i> = 0.92	<i>p</i> = 1.0
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.2 +0.3 / -1.7	7	8.8 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.6]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.8			<i>p</i> = 0.75	<i>p</i> = 0.83
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.4 / -2.1	5	8.5 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.87				<i>p</i> = 0.92
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.6	7	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.97				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 4: *De fixe</i>	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	... +... / -...	–	0.3 +0.6 / -0.2 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.2]	29					

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 5: Pour certain</i>	2.2 +1.6 / -1.3	34	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1	34	4.4 +3.8 / -2.3	7	2.6 +1.3 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.1 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	2.9 +1.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	2.5 +2.4 / -1.9	17	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	2.9 +1.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.2]	29					
Younger speakers	1.9 +2.2 / -1.6	18	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	2.8 +1.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 0.67$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	2.7 +2.5 / -2.0	16	2.1 +2.4 / -1.7	16	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	3.3 +1.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.2]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.6 +2.2 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.5]	29	$p = 0.93$		$p = 0.63$	$p = 0.67$	$p = 0.76$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5	10	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5	10	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.0 +1.8 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.59$			$p = 0.36$	$p = 0.86$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	4.2 +2.2 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.54$				$p = 0.46$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.76$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 6: En continu</i>	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8	34	6.7 +1.6 / -1.9	34	5.8 +1.2 / -1.2	25	6.9 +0.9 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.8 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8	17	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	6.5 +1.5 / -1.5	13	7.0 +1.1 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.4]	29	$p = 0.76$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8	17	6.9 +2.1 / -2.8	17	5.7 +2.0 / -1.8	12	6.7 +1.3 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.4]	29					

Younger speakers	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	18	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	18	7.0 +1.1 / -1.2	16	7.8 +0.9 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.09^6$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	6.7 +2.2 / -2.9	16	5.0 +2.5 / -2.7	16	4.0 +3.6 / -2.0	9	5.5 +1.6 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.5]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	6.3 +2.3 / -2.1	7	7.1 +1.4 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.2 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.56$		$p = 0.67$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.04$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	6.4 +1.9 / -1.8	9	7.6 +1.1 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.22$			$p = 0.67$	$p = 0.01$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	4.6 +3.9 / -2.4	6	7.1 +1.4 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.55$				$p = 0.04$
Speakers aged 66 or more	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	4.2 +2.2 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.05$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5		
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 7: À drette</i>	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9	34	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9	34	4.6 +3.9 / -2.4	6	5.3 +1.4 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.1]	29	
Female speakers	5.8 +2.3 / -2.7	17	5.8 +2.3 / -2.7	17	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	5.6 +1.7 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.5]	29	$p = 0.87$ Not sign.
Male speakers	5.3 +2.4 / -2.7	17	5.3 +2.4 / -2.7	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	5.4 +1.7 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.5]	29	
Younger speakers	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3	18	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3	18	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	4.3 +1.8 / -1.6	29	$p = 0.09^7$

⁶ $P=0.02$ (weak dependency) using the student's two-sample t -test in Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Nevertheless, this test is potentially less reliable insofar as the calculator's current version averages the two-tailed uncertainties.

⁷ $P=0.04$ (weak dependency) using the student's two-sample t -test in Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Nevertheless, this test is potentially less reliable insofar as the calculator's current version averages the two-tailed uncertainties.

							[83% CI: +1.5 / -1.4]		Not sign.				
Elder speakers	7.3 +2.0 / -2.9	16	7.3 +2.0 / -2.9	16	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	6.8 +1.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.6]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	5.9 +2.1 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.8 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.87$		$p = 0.09$	$p = 0.64$	$p = 0.58$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.5 +2.0 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.4]	29	$p = 0.04$			$p = 0.03$	$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	6.6 +1.8 / -2.4 [83% CI: +1.6 / -2.1]	29	$p = 0.44$				$p = 0.9$
Speakers aged 66 or more	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	... +... / -...	–	6.8 +2.0 / -2.9 [83% CI: +1.7 / -2.5]	29	$p = 0.41$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 8.1: En especial</i>	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.2 +1.2 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29		$p = 0.007$ Significant, weak depend.			
Male speakers	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	... +... / -...	–	0.6 +1.1 / -0.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.3]	29					
Younger speakers	0.9 +1.9 / -0.9	18	0.9 +1.9 / -0.9	18	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.0]	29		$p = 0.9$ Not sign.			
Elder speakers	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.6 +1.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.25$		$p = 0.03$	$p = 0.06$	$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	... +... / -...	–	0.9 +1.7 / -0.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -0.5]	29	$p = 0.09$			$p = 0.83$	$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.22$				$p = 0.06$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.25$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 8.2: En spécial</i>	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.5 +0.1 / -0.4	34	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.4 +0.2 / -0.7	17	9.2 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7	17	9.2 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	9.4 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.4 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7	18	9.1 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.86$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.5 +0.2 / -0.8	16	9.2 +0.4 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.4 +0.2 / -1.5	8	8.7 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.95$		$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.6 +0.2 / -1.3	10	8.9 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.83$		$p = 0.83$	$p = 0.83$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.5 +0.2 / -1.6	8	8.7 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.95$				$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.4 +0.2 / -1.5	8	8.7 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.95$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 9: À l'extrême</i>	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7	34	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7	34	8.3 +0.5 / -0.7	30	8.4 +0.6 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.8]	29					
Female speakers	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8	17	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8	17	8.2 +0.7 / -1.1	14	7.8 +1.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.32$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	8.4 +0.6 / -1.0	16	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29					
Younger speakers	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	18	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	18	8.2 +0.7 / -1.1	16	8.2 +0.8 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.85$				

Elder speakers	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	8.5 +0.5 / -1.1	14	8.2 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29	Not sign.				
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.8 +0.6 / -1.7	8	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.37$		$p = 0.22$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.17$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	10	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	10	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6	8	7.3 +1.3 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.8]	29	$p = 0.53$			$p = 0.22$	$p = 0.81$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4	8	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.37$				$p = 0.17$
Speakers aged 66 or more	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8	6	7.0 +1.6 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.4 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.39$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 10: En gros</i>	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	8.6 +0.4 / -0.7	32	8.9 +0.5 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.7]	29					
Female speakers	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.7 +0.5 / -1.1	15	8.3 +0.8 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.32$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	8.5 +0.6 / -1.0	17	9.0 +0.5 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.2 +0.2 / -0.7	18	9.2 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.12$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	7.6 +0.9 / -1.2	14	8.0 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.0 +0.3 / -1.4	8	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.59$		$p = 0.74$	$p = 0.55$	$p = 0.22$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.2 / -1.2	10	8.9 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.31$			$p = 0.34$	$p = 0.12$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	6.6 +1.9 / -1.8	8	8.0 +0.9 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.83$				$p = 0.49$
Speakers aged 66 or more	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8	6	7.2 +1.5 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.33$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 11: À l'improviste	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	8.3 +0.4 / -0.6	34	9.2 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	8.3 +0.5 / -0.9	17	8.9 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	8.3 +0.5 / -0.9	17	8.9 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	8.4 +0.5 / -0.9	18	9.0 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.86$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	8.3 +0.6 / -1.0	16	8.9 +0.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6	8	8.3 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.8$		$p = 0.59$	$p = 0.84$	$p = 0.92$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	8.9 +0.2 / -1.1	10	8.8 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.66$			$p = 0.74$	$p = 0.67$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.5 +0.6 / -1.5	8	8.5 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 1.0$				$p = 0.92$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	6	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	6	8.1 +0.9 / -1.5	6	8.4 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.9$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2)		

							+ 1x B.1) : 5							
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 12: Au large</i>	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7	34	8.1 +1.2 / -1.8	34	6.9 +0.8 / -0.9	26	7.9 +0.7 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.6 / -0.8]	29						
Female speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	7.2 +1.1 / -1.2	15	8.3 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.19 Not sign.					
Male speakers	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8	17	6.9 +2.1 / -2.8	17	6.9 +1.4 / -1.5	11	7.2 +1.1 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.4]	29						
Younger speakers	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	18	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	18	7.4 +0.9 / -1.1	15	7.7 +1.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.97 Not sign.					
Elder speakers	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9	16	6.4 +1.7 / -1.7	11	7.7 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29						
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.2 +1.5 / -1.7	8	8.2 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.40		<i>p</i> = 0.22	<i>p</i> = 0.85	<i>p</i> = 0.3	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	6.8 +2.6 / -3.7	10	6.8 +2.6 / -3.7	10	8.0 +1.1 / -1.7	7	6.8 +1.6 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.8]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.48			<i>p</i> = 0.3	<i>p</i> = 0.87	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	6.6 +2.3 / -2.1	6	8.0 +0.9 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.56				<i>p</i> = 0.39	
Speakers aged 66 or more	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1	5	7.0 +1.4 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -2.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.62					
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 13: De léger</i>	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.2 +1.2 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.9]	29						
Female speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.					
Male speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29						
Younger speakers	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	... +... / -...	–	0.6 +1.0 / -0.4 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.08 ⁸ Not sign.					
Elder speakers	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +... / -...]	29						
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.45		<i>p</i> = 0.83	<i>p</i> = 0.03	<i>p</i> = 1.0	

⁸ *P*=0.008 (weak dependency) using the student's two-sample *t*-test in Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Nevertheless, this test is potentially less reliable insofar as the calculator's current version averages the two-tailed uncertainties.

Speakers aged 30 to 45	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	... +... / -...	–	0.9 +1.7 / -0.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -0.5]	29	$p = 0.24$			$p = 0.01$	$p = 0.83$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.8 +2.2 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.06$				$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 66 or more	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.45$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 14: À plein	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9	34	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9	34	5.5 +1.6 / -1.5	19	5.4 +1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.0]	29					
Female speakers	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	4.5 +2.9 / -2.0	11	5.8 +1.5 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	29	$p = 0.57$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	7.2 +1.5 / -1.7	8	5.2 +1.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	2.9 +2.4 / -2.0	18	2.9 +2.4 / -2.0	18	5.0 +4.1 / -2.6	5	3.5 +1.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.001$ Significant, strong depend.				
Elder speakers	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	6.3 +1.5 / -1.5	14	7.6 +1.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.3]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.8 +2.2 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.11$		$p = 0.94$	$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.01$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	3.2 +3.3 / -2.6	10	3.2 +3.3 / -2.6	10	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	3.9 +2.1 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.5]	29	$p = 0.12$			$p = 0.02$	$p = 0.01$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	5.4 +3.0 / -2.2	7	7.1 +1.4 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.2 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.15$				$p = 0.69$
Speakers aged 66 or more	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	7.5 +1.4 / -1.7	7	7.6 +1.3 / -2.3	29	$p =$				

							[83% CI: +1.1 / -2.0]		0.05				
<i>Item 15: De *plene</i>	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	... +... / -...	-	0.3 +0.6 / -0.2	29					
							[83% CI: +0.5 / -0.2]						

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (P =)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St- Jean] <i>Item 16: De sec</i>	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.2 +1.2 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	... +... / -...	-	0.6 +1.1 / -0.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.007 Significant, weak depend.				
Male speakers	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.7 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.15 ⁹ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	0.4 +1.7 / -0.4	16	0.4 +1.7 / -0.4	16	... +... / -...	-	0.6 +1.2 / -0.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.3]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	-	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.46		<i>p</i> = 0.04	<i>p</i> = 1.0	<i>p</i> = 1.0
Speakers aged 30 to 45	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.5 +2.0 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.4]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.07			<i>p</i> = 0.04	<i>p</i> = 0.04
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	-	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.46				<i>p</i> = 1.0
Speakers aged 66 or more	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	-	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8	29	<i>p</i> = 0.46				

⁹ *P*=0.01 (significant, weak dependency) using the student's two-sample *t*-test in Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Nevertheless, this test is potentially less reliable insofar as the calculator's current version averages the two-tailed uncertainties.

							[83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 17: D'ordinaire</i>	9.0 +0.9 / -1.6	34	9.0 +0.9 / -1.6	34	5.5 +2.4 / -2.0	10	7.9 +0.9 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.8 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	4.6 +3.9 / -2.4	6	7.6 +1.2 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.74 Not sign.				
Male speakers	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1	4	7.9 +1.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	18	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	18	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	7.1 +1.5 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.47 Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	6.6 +2.3 / -2.1	6	8.4 +0.8 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.2]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	... +... / -...	–	7.8 +1.6 / -3.0 [83% CI: +1.4 / -2.6]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.89		<i>p</i> = 0.45	<i>p</i> = 1.0	<i>p</i> = 0.77
Speakers aged 30 to 45	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	10	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	10	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4	6.7 +1.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.8]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.38			<i>p</i> = 0.39	<i>p</i> = 0.21
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	7.8 +1.3 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.86				<i>p</i> = 0.72
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1	4	8.2 +0.9 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.51				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5		
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 18: Pour le sûr</i>	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	0.8 +1.2 / -0.7	34	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	2.1 +1.3 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.1 / -0.9]	29	
Female speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.4 +1.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.91

Male speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29	Not sign.				
Younger speakers	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.2 +1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.9]	29	$p = 0.08$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.1]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.1$		$p = 0.18$	$p = 0.06$	$p = 0.06$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.4 +1.5 / -1.1 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.92$			$p = 0.46$	$p = 0.46$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.45$				$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.45$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 19: Au sérieux</i>	9.5 +0.5 / -1.4	34	9.5 +0.5 / -1.4	34	8.8 +0.4 / -0.6	33	9.1 +0.4 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.6]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.1 +0.2 / -0.7	17	9.1 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 0.44$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	8.3 +0.7 / -1.1	16	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29					
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.0 +0.4 / -0.9	18	9.1 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.5$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	8.5 +0.5 / -1.0	15	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.3]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.3 +1.0 / -1.7	8	8.4 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 1.0$		$p = 0.59$	$p = 0.84$	$p = 0.53$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.5 +0.2 / -1.3	10	8.9 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.47$			$p = 0.74$	$p = 0.25$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4	8	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.80$				$p = 0.41$
Speakers aged 66 or more	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.0 +1.1 / -1.7	7	7.7 +1.2 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.46$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 20: Pour vrai</i>	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	9.2 +0.7 / -1.6	32	8.7 +0.3 / -0.6	30	8.9 +0.5 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.7]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	8.6 +0.5 / -0.9	17	9.0 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.33 Not sign.				
Male speakers	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.4 +1.5 / -2.9	15	8.8 +0.4 / -1.1	13	8.3 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.4	18	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	9.2 +0.2 / -0.8	15	8.8 +0.7 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.74 Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	8.2 +0.6 / -1.0	15	8.5 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.3]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.1 +0.9 / -4.8	6	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8	6	8.4 +0.8 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.83		<i>p</i> = 0.92	<i>p</i> = 0.49	<i>p</i> = 0.84
Speakers aged 30 to 45	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	9.3 +0.2 / -1.4	9	8.3 +1.0 / -2.0 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.93			<i>p</i> = 0.54	<i>p</i> = 0.77
Speakers aged 46 to 65	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	7.5 +1.4 / -1.7	7	7.6 +1.3 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.52				<i>p</i> = 0.37
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4	8	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.64				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 21: En brave</i>	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9	34	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9	34	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	7.1 +1.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2]	29					
Female speakers	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	... +... / -...	–	6.3 +1.7 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.23 Not sign.				
Male speakers	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	7.7 +1.3 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.5]	29					

Younger speakers	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7	18	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7	18	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	6.8 +1.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.5]	29	$p = 0.64$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9	16	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9	16	... +... / -...	–	7.7 +1.4 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.8]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	6.0 +2.0 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.8 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.42$		$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.25$	$p = 0.62$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	10	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	10	... +... / -...	–	7.3 +1.7 / -2.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -2.3]	29	$p = 0.79$			$p = 0.75$	$p = 0.75$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	... +... / -...	–	7.8 +1.6 / -3.0 [83% CI: +1.4 / -2.6]	29	$p = 0.52$				$p = 0.55$
Speakers aged 66 or more	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	... +... / -...	–	6.8 +2.0 / -2.9 [83% CI: +1.7 / -2.5]	29	$p = 0.9$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 22: De court	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	9.1 +0.8 / -1.8	28	8.8 +0.2 / -0.6	24	8.9 +0.5 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.7]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.6	15	8.7 +0.3 / -1.0	14	9.0 +0.4 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 0.27$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.1 +1.7 / -3.2	13	8.9 +0.2 / -1.1	10	8.2 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.4	18	8.8 +1.2 / -3.1	13	8.9 +0.2 / -1.1	10	8.6 +0.7 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.99$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	9.0 +1.0 / -2.8	15	8.7 +0.3 / -1.0	14	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.3]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65

Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	5	9.0 +0.4 / -2.6	4	8.3 +0.9 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.86$		$p = 0.78$	$p = 0.92$	$p = 0.72$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8	6	8.0 +1.1 / -2.0 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.8]	29	$p = 0.86$			$p = 0.7$	$p = 0.93$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.2 +0.8 / -4.4	7	8.5 +0.7 / -1.7	7	8.4 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.76$				$p = 0.65$
Speakers aged 66 or more	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.6	7	7.9 +1.2 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.0 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.79$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 23: À mal</i>	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1	34	1.6 +1.5 / -1.1	34	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.0]	29					
Female speakers	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	... +... / -...	–	1.6 +1.6 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.4 / -0.9]	29	$p = 0.13$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.1 +1.6 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.2]	29					
Younger speakers	1.9 +2.2 / -1.6	18	1.9 +2.2 / -1.6	18	... +... / -...	–	2.0 +1.6 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.88$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.6 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.1]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	... +... / -...	–	2.1 +2.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +2.2 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.78$		$p = 0.72$	$p = 0.22$	$p = 0.41$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	... +... / -...	–	2.6 +2.3 / -1.7 [83% CI: +2.0 / -1.5]	29	$p = 0.86$			$p = 0.39$	$p = 0.22$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.8 +2.2 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.21$				$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 66 or more	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.13$				
<i>Item 24: De *diaire</i>	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	... +... / -...	–	0.3 +0.6 / -0.2 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.2]	29					
<i>Item 25: (*)De seguide</i>	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	... +... / -...	–	0.3 +0.6 / -0.2 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.2]	29					

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 26: À blanc</i>	1.3 +1.4 / -1.0	34	1.3 +1.4 / -1.0	34	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1	4	2.8 +0.9 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.8 / -0.7]	29					
Female speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.29 Not sign.				
Male speakers	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	2.0 +2.3 / -1.6	17	7.8 +1.7 / -2.4	3	3.4 +1.3 / -1.1 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29					
Younger speakers	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.7 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.69 Not sign.				
Elder speakers	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	1.5 +2.3 / -1.4	16	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3	2	3.2 +1.3 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.1]	29					
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.10		<i>p</i> = 0.04	<i>p</i> = 1.0	<i>p</i> = 0.01
Speakers aged 30 to 45	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	3.5 +2.0 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.4]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.30			<i>p</i> = 0.04	<i>p</i> = 0.59
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.10				<i>p</i> = 0.01
Speakers aged 66 or more	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3	2	4.2 +2.0 / -1.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.5]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.10				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 27: En clair</i>	3.9 +1.8 / -1.7	34	3.9 +1.8 / -1.7	34	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	4.5 +1.4 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.2]	29					
Female speakers	4.2 +2.5 / -2.5	17	4.2 +2.5 / -2.5	17	... +... / -...	–	4.2 +1.9 / -1.9 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.94 Not sign.				
Male speakers	3.6 +2.5 / -2.3	17	3.6 +2.5 / -2.3	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	4.3 +1.7 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.4]	29					
Younger speakers	4.5 +2.4 / -2.5	18	4.5 +2.4 / -2.5	18	... +... / -...	–	4.5 +1.8 / -1.9 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.54				

Elder speakers	3.3 +2.6 / -2.2	16	3.3 +2.6 / -2.2	16	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	4.1 +1.7 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.4]	29	Not sign.				
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	... +... / -...	–	3.1 +2.6 / -2.0 [83% CI: +2.3 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.44$		$p = 0.1$	$p = 0.16$	$p = 0.5$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5	10	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5	10	... +... / -...	–	5.8 +2.2 / -2.6 [83% CI: +1.9 / -2.3]	29	$p = 0.19$			$p = 0.75$	$p = 0.02$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	5.3 +2.1 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.31$				$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	... +... / -...	–	2.1 +2.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +2.2 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.09$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 28: À couvert</i>	5.3 +1.7 / -1.9	34	5.0 +1.8 / -1.9	32	5.5 +1.8 / -1.6	16	5.1 +1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.0]	29					
Female speakers	5.8 +2.3 / -2.7	17	5.3 +2.6 / -2.8	15	6.0 +2.4 / -2.0	8	5.6 +1.5 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	29	$p = 0.52$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	6.0 +2.4 / -2.0	8	4.9 +1.5 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.4]	29					
Younger speakers	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6	18	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6	18	6.4 +1.9 / -1.8	9	5.2 +1.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.93$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	5.6 +2.4 / -2.8	16	5.0 +2.7 / -2.9	14	5.4 +3.0 / -2.2	7	5.3 +1.6 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.5]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	6.5 +3.0 / -2.3	4	5.3 +2.1 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.8]	29	$p = 0.93$		$p = 0.94$	$p = 0.79$	$p = 0.95$

Speakers aged 30 to 45	5.0 +3.1 / -3.3	10	5.0 +3.1 / -3.3	10	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1	5	5.4 +1.8 / -1.9 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.7]	29	$p = 1.0$			$p = 0.83$	$p = 0.88$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	5.0 +4.1 / -2.6	5	5.7 +2.1 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.8 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.8$				$p = 0.74$
Speakers aged 66 or more	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	3.6 +4.1 / -3.3	6	7.4 +2.5 / -2.3	2	5.2 +2.1 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.8]	29	$p = 0.86$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 29: En dernier</i>	4.7 +1.8 / -1.8	34	4.2 +1.8 / -1.8	34	6.5 +1.3 / -1.4	15	4.9 +1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	4.2 +2.5 / -2.5	17	3.6 +2.5 / -2.3	17	5.4 +3.0 / -2.2	7	4.3 +1.6 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.4 / -1.3]	29		$p = 0.22$ Not sign.			
Male speakers	5.3 +2.4 / -2.7	17	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6	8	5.6 +1.4 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3	18	4.0 +2.5 / -2.3	18	6.0 +2.4 / -2.0	8	4.5 +1.5 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.2]	29		$p = 0.44$ Not sign.			
Elder speakers	5.6 +2.4 / -2.8	16	4.4 +2.6 / -2.6	16	7.5 +1.4 / -1.7	7	5.7 +1.4 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.5]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1	5	6.1 +1.9 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.42$		$p = 0.05$	$p = 0.38$	$p = 0.83$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	2.4 +3.2 / -2.1	10	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	3.4 +2.0 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.4]	29	$p = 0.09$			$p = 0.32$	$p = 0.03$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	2.9 +3.6 / -2.6	8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	4.8 +2.2 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.75$				$p = 0.28$
Speakers aged 66 or more	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	8.3 +1.0 / -2.1	5	6.4 +1.8 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.27$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 30: Par exprès</i>	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.4 +0.1 / -0.4	32	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.2 / -0.6]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.4 +0.2 / -0.8	15	9.2 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 1.0 Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.4 +0.2 / -0.7	17	9.2 +0.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.5 +0.2 / -0.7	18	9.3 +0.4 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.3 / -1.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.75 Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.2 +0.2 / -0.9	14	9.1 +0.4 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.4 +0.2 / -1.5	8	8.7 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 1.0		<i>p</i> = 0.83	<i>p</i> = 1.0	<i>p</i> = 0.84
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.6 +0.2 / -1.3	10	8.9 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.6]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.77			<i>p</i> = 0.83	<i>p</i> = 0.66
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.5 +0.2 / -1.6	8	8.7 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -0.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 1.0				<i>p</i> = 0.84
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.8	6	8.5 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.8				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 31: En grand</i>	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.1 +0.3 / -1.5	8	9.3 +0.3 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.6]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.1 +0.3 / -1.9	6	9.0 +0.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.79 Not sign.				
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.4 +0.2 / -5.5	2	8.8 +0.7 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.5]	29					

Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3	2	8.8 +0.6 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.83$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.2 +0.3 / -2.0	6	9.0 +0.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.2]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.0 +0.6 / -4.3	2	8.3 +0.9 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.82$		$p = 0.58$	$p = 0.93$	$p = 0.93$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	... +... / -...	–	8.9 +0.8 / -2.4 [83% CI: +0.7 / -2.1]	29	$p = 0.65$			$p = 0.65$	$p = 0.65$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.0 +0.5 / -3.3	3	8.4 +0.9 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.91$				$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.4 +0.2 / -4.2	3	8.4 +0.9 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.91$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 32: Allège	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	8.4 +0.4 / -0.6	32	8.8 +0.5 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.7]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	8.1 +0.6 / -1.0	17	8.8 +0.5 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29	$p = 0.47$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.8 +0.4 / -0.9	15	8.3 +0.8 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	18	8.6 +1.2 / -2.6	18	8.3 +0.6 / -1.0	16	8.3 +0.8 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.5$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	8.5 +0.4 / -0.9	16	8.9 +0.4 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.1]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65

Speakers aged 18 to 29	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.6 +0.7 / -1.8	7	7.8 +1.2 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.66$		$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.59$	$p = 0.46$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	8.2 +0.8 / -1.4	9	8.0 +1.0 / -2.0 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.81$			$p = 0.70$	$p = 0.55$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.1 +0.9 / -1.5	8	8.4 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.81$				$p = 0.84$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	8.9 +0.3 / -1.4	8	8.6 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.61$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 33: Au long</i>	1.0 +1.3 / -0.9	34	1.0 +1.3 / -0.9	34	5.8 +4.2 / -3.0	3	2.2 +1.3 / -1.0 [83% CI: +1.2 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29	$p = 0.75$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	1.5 +2.2 / -1.3	17	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.8 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29					
Younger speakers	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	1.4 +2.1 / -1.3	18	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	2	2.7 +1.5 / -1.3 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.1]	29	$p = 0.31$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.6 +1.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.55$		$p = 0.86$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.06$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5	10	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5	10	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.0 +1.8 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.67$			$p = 0.86$	$p = 0.08$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.55$				$p = 0.06$
Speakers aged 66 or more	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.07$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 34: En neuf</i>	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9	34	7.5 +1.4 / -1.9	34	7.3 +0.8 / -0.9	27	7.3 +0.8 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8	17	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8	17	7.9 +0.9 / -1.2	14	7.4 +1.2 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.75 Not sign.				
Male speakers	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8	17	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8	17	6.9 +1.3 / -1.4	13	7.1 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.4]	29					
Younger speakers	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7	18	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7	18	6.9 +1.4 / -1.4	14	6.9 +1.2 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.4 Not sign.				
Elder speakers	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9	16	7.9 +1.7 / -2.9	16	7.8 +0.8 / -1.2	13	7.6 +1.1 / -1.6 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.4]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	5	5.0 +2.2 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.9 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.11		<i>p</i> = 0.03	<i>p</i> = 0.34	<i>p</i> = 0.01
Speakers aged 30 to 45	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	7.9 +1.1 / -1.5	9	8.0 +1.1 / -2.0 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.23			<i>p</i> = 0.2	<i>p</i> = 0.77
Speakers aged 46 to 65	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	6.1 +3.1 / -3.9	8	8.3 +1.0 / -2.1	5	6.4 +1.8 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.63				<i>p</i> = 0.12
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6	8	8.3 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.11				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 35: A noir</i>	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	0.2 +0.8 / -0.2	34	... +... / -...	–	0.3 +0.6 / -0.2 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.2]	29					

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency (<i>P</i> =)				
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5						
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 36: Au parfait</i>	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5	34	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5	34	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.1 +1.1 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.01 Significant, weak depend.				
Male speakers	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	... +... / -...	–	0.6 +1.1 / -0.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.3]	29					
Younger speakers	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	... +... / -...	–	0.6 +1.0 / -0.4 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.14 ¹⁰ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.6 +1.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.56		<i>p</i> = 0.83	<i>p</i> = 0.06	<i>p</i> = 1.0
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	... +... / -...	–	0.9 +1.7 / -0.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -0.5]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.32			<i>p</i> = 0.03	<i>p</i> = 0.83
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.09				<i>p</i> = 0.06
Speakers aged 66 or more	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.56				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 37: À la rebours</i>	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5	34	0.5 +1.1 / -0.5	34	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	1.4 +1.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2]	29					
Female speakers	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	0.4 +1.6 / -0.4	17	... +... / -...	–	0.6 +1.1 / -0.4 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.3]	29	<i>p</i> = 0.01 Significant, weak depend.				
Male speakers	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	0.9 +2.0 / -0.9	17	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.5 +1.3 / -1.2	29					

¹⁰ *P*=0.008 (significant, weak dependency) using the student's two-sample *t*-test in Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Nevertheless, this test is potentially less reliable insofar as the calculator's current version averages the two-tailed uncertainties.

							[83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]							
Younger speakers	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	0.4 +1.5 / -0.4	18	... +... / -...	–	0.6 +1.0 / -0.4 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.3]	29	$p = 0.14^{11}$ Not sign.					
Elder speakers	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	1.0 +2.1 / -1.0	16	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	2.6 +1.4 / -1.2 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.0]	29						
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.56$		$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.06$	
Speakers aged 30 to 45	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6	10	... +... / -...	–	0.9 +1.7 / -0.6 [83% CI: +1.5 / -0.5]	29	$p = 0.32$			$p = 0.83$	$p = 0.03$	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	0.7 +3.0 / -0.7	8	... +... / -...	–	1.1 +2.1 / -0.8 [83% CI: +1.8 / -0.7]	29	$p = 0.56$				$p = 0.06$	
Speakers aged 66 or more	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	1.8 +3.5 / -1.8	8	6.7 +3.3 / -3.5	1	3.2 +2.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.09$					

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)
Weighting / combination	double-weighted		simple-weighted		simple-weighted		(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5		
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] Item 38: De travers	9.2 +0.7 / -1.5	34	9.2 +0.7 / -1.6	32	8.4 +0.4 / -0.8	20	8.8 +0.5 / -0.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.7]	29	
Female speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	8.3 +0.7 / -1.3	10	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29	$p = 1.0$ Not sign.
Male speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	8.6 +0.5 / -1.3	10	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29	
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	8.6 +0.5 / -1.4	9	8.9 +0.5 / -1.2	29	$p = 0.36$

¹¹ $P=0.008$ (significant, weak dependency) using the student's two-sample t -test in Roy's calculator (2021-2022). Nevertheless, this test is potentially less reliable insofar as the calculator's current version averages the two-tailed uncertainties.

							[83% CI: +0.4 / -1.0]		Not sign.				
Elder speakers	8.5 +1.4 / -2.8	16	8.4 +1.5 / -2.9	15	8.3 +0.7 / -1.3	11	8.1 +0.9 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.3]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.2 +0.8 / -4.4	7	8.1 +1.3 / -2.3	4	8.3 +0.9 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.79$		$p = 0.76$	$p = 0.33$	$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	8.9 +0.4 / -2.1	5	8.6 +0.7 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.6]	29	$p = 0.48$			$p = 0.19$	$p = 0.75$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	6.8 +2.8 / -4.3	7	8.9 +0.4 / -2.1	5	7.1 +1.6 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.4 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.35$				$p = 0.32$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8	6	8.3 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.78$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 39: Pantoute</i>	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	9.8 +0.2 / -1.3	34	... +... / -...	–	9.6 +0.3 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]	29					
Female speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	... +... / -...	–	9.3 +0.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.5]	29		$p = 1.0$ Not sign.			
Male speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	9.6 +0.4 / -2.4	17	... +... / -...	–	9.3 +0.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.5]	29					
Younger speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	9.6 +0.4 / -2.2	18	... +... / -...	–	9.3 +0.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.3]	29		$p = 0.88$ Not sign.			
Elder speakers	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	9.6 +0.4 / -2.5	16	... +... / -...	–	9.2 +0.5 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.5]	29					
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	... +... / -...	–	8.7 +0.9 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.4]	29	$p = 0.96$		$p = 0.87$	$p = 1.0$	$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	10	... +... / -...	–	8.9 +0.8 / -2.4 [83% CI: +0.7 / -2.1]	29	$p = 0.87$			$p = 0.87$	$p = 0.87$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	... +... / -...	–	8.7 +0.9 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.4]	29	$p = 0.96$				$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	... +... / -...	–	8.7 +0.9 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.4]	29	$p = 0.96$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	# Response (A.1)	Local recognition (A.2)	# Response (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	# Response (B.1)	II. Vitality (median value) (scale 1-10)	Degree of freedom (Vitality)	III. Significance of group dependency ($P =$)				
									Weighting / combination	double-weighted	simple-weighted	simple-weighted	(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 40: En premier</i>	8.7 +1.0 / -1.7	34	8.1 +1.2 / -1.8	34	8.2 +0.5 / -0.7	28	8.3 +0.6 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.6 / -0.8]	29					
Female speakers	9.1 +0.9 / -2.6	17	8.5 +1.3 / -2.7	17	8.8 +0.4 / -0.9	15	8.6 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.2]	29	$p = 0.17$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	8.0 +1.6 / -2.8	17	7.5 +1.9 / -2.8	17	7.5 +1.0 / -1.2	13	7.5 +1.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.3]	29					
Younger speakers	8.1 +1.5 / -2.7	18	7.1 +2.0 / -2.7	18	8.7 +0.4 / -1.1	13	7.8 +1.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.59$ Not sign.				
Elder speakers	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	9.0 +1.0 / -2.7	16	7.7 +0.8 / -1.1	15	8.4 +0.7 / -1.4 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.3]	29					
									18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	9.1 +0.3 / -1.9	6	7.2 +1.5 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.6$		$p = 0.68$	$p = 0.69$	$p = 0.34$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7	10	6.8 +2.6 / -3.7	10	8.5 +0.7 / -1.7	7	7.7 +1.2 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.98$			$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.57$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8	8.0 +1.1 / -1.7	7	7.7 +1.2 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.98$				$p = 0.59$
Speakers aged 66 or more	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8	7.6 +1.2 / -1.6	8	8.3 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]	29	$p = 0.49$				
French [Saguenay–Lac-St-Jean] <i>Item 41: Au ras</i>	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9	34	5.6 +1.7 / -1.9	34	7.3 +0.8 / -1.0	21	5.9 +1.0 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.9]	29					
Female speakers	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	4.7 +2.5 / -2.6	17	7.4 +1.3 / -1.5	9	5.3 +1.5 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.3 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.24$ Not sign.				
Male speakers	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	6.4 +2.2 / -2.8	17	7.4 +1.1 / -1.3	12	6.5 +1.3 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.4]	29					
Younger speakers	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6	18	5.0 +2.4 / -2.6	18	7.3 +1.2 / -1.4	11	5.5 +1.4 / -1.5 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.3]	29	$p = 0.42$				

Elder speakers	6.2 +2.3 / -2.9	16	6.2 +2.3 / -2.9	16	7.5 +1.2 / -1.4	10	6.4 +1.4 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.4]	29	Not sign.				
										18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	8	3.9 +3.6 / -3.2	8	7.8 +1.7 / -2.4	3	4.8 +2.1 / -1.9 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.35$		$p = 0.37$	$p = 0.11$	$p = 0.62$
Speakers aged 30 to 45	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5	10	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5	10	7.2 +1.5 / -1.7	8	6.0 +1.7 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.5 / -1.7]	29	$p = 0.87$			$p = 0.44$	$p = 0.71$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.1 +2.5 / -4.1	8	7.8 +1.3 / -1.8	6	7.0 +1.6 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.4 / -2.0]	29	$p = 0.27$				$p = 0.28$
Speakers aged 66 or more	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	5.0 +3.4 / -3.6	8	7.3 +2.1 / -2.1	4	5.5 +2.0 / -2.1 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.8]	29	$p = 0.77$				

Table 2.3: Combining data. The adverbials' vitality (based on A.1, A.2 and B.1)

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